

STUDY IN DETERMINING RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PRINCIPAL'S LEADERSHIP STYLES PRACTICES AND TEACHERS JOB SATISFACTION AT DEGREE COLLEGES IN NORTH BANGALORE CITY

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Abstract

Determined leaders are the real source of success for any organisation they work in the light of bringing the vision into reality. Their role as leaders in educational institutional set up is more vivid and crucial in keeping the stake holders satisfied. With this prospect study is undertaken to understand the relationship that exists between Principal's Leadership practices and teachers Job satisfaction at degree colleges in Bangalore city. For the purpose of research 10 colleges working in north Bangalore city was chosen, among them 120 teachers were chosen under purposive sampling method. The data was gathered through structured questionnaire having Principal's leadership styles as independent variable and teachers job satisfaction dependent variable. Correlation analysis was performed in determining the job satisfaction of teachers. The results revealed that there do exist a positive relationship between Principal's servant and transformational leadership practices at degree colleges where transformational leadership was practiced less and laissez faire leadership had the negative relationship in determining the job satisfaction of teachers.

Keywords: Leadership Styles, Educational Leadership, Job Satisfaction

1. INTRODUCTION

Knowledge creation is being the key source of development which are acquired through continuous learning and development. The process of knowledge acquisition will not have end means but results in betterment of human life. Knowledge driven society has gained prominence due to advancement in technology and related applications.

To such knowledge creation process higher educational institutions play a pivotal role to develop and mold students to reach the desired goals through assistance and support from the educational institutions. Higher educational institutions have transformed drastically over the years, in terms of their performance and quality delivery. Such success is possible through able leadership and passionate performance of teaching fraternity working under the institutions.

Educational leaders serve as a guide and influence the other educators working with them for the delivery of quality services to the pupil. These leaders focus on quality learning process along with students' development. Educational leadership studies are mostly identified with lower primary, primary and secondary education but higher educational leadership significance and requirement are understudied in Indian context.

Leadership analysis and study is very much essential even at higher educational institutions. Academic leaders role in higher educational institutions will assist and help the students to perform better and chose a right type of career.

There are majorly four types of educational leadership identified which are widely used, all the four leadership styles have greater implications on educational institutions setup, each leadership relevance is discussed as under:

Every successful position requires an able leadership management which takes up the responsibility of its success and decision made. Even at higher educational institutions the leaders in the position of president, vice president, Dean, Principal articulate the institutional vision to reality. It is a long term and continuous process of making vision into real time achievable goals. The leadership framework at higher educational institutions are quite different from that of other organizational set up, here the stakeholders are the students whose future is well built and molded under the supervision of the institutions. Students are transformed through able guidance and support from the staff who have the passion and expertized knowledge to be shared among the students.

Higher educational institution have developed tremendously from past years with nearing to thousand of Universities operating both at public and private owned universities with thousands of affiliated colleges working with the Universities. The leaders who are in charge of these institutions and universities play a pivotal role. Both leaders and teaches at the universities together help towards the development of the nation.

Leadership behavior practiced by management will ensure proper guidance, motivation and support to the staff members. A happy worker is one who is satisfied at his work. Keeping the staff members satisfied at their work will contribute maximum for overall development.

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With the above prospective the study is being initiated to identify the connection between college Principal's leadership behaviour and College teachers job satisfaction at North Bangalore city.

Major educational leadership namely Transformational, Transactional, Laissez fair and Servant leadership style has been assessed in identifying the connection between Job Satisfaction of Degree College Teachers at the city.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The definitions on leadership and job satisfaction gives more insight about the concepts and past literature work done in the area of leadership styles practiced by Principals and its relationship in determining job satisfaction of teachers are discussed here to provide more insights and connectivity of the variables under study. Some of the literary works are listed below

"Leadership may be considered as the process (act) of influencing the activities of an organized group in its efforts toward goal setting and goal achievement"- Stogdill (1950, p3)

"Leadership is the influence increment over and above mechanical compliance with the routine directives of the organisation "- Katz & Kahn (1978, p.528)

The term job satisfactions refers to the attitude and feelings people have about their work. Positive and favorable attitudes towards the job indicate job satisfaction. Negative and unfavorable attitudes towards the job indicate job dissatisfaction (Armstrong, 2006).

Vroom in his definition on job satisfaction focuses on the role of the employee in the workplace. Thus he defines job satisfaction as affective orientations on the part of individuals toward work roles which they are presently occupying (Vroom, 1964).

Hijazi et al (2016) conducted the survey in the state of UAE private universities on determining the job satisfaction of employees working under those universities and leadership style practiced by the top management with quantitative analysis. Opinions were collected based on the participation of the respondents chosen on random sampling technique and the results revealed that transformational leadership style had a positive impact on employee job satisfaction in comparison with transactional leadership style which exhibited the negative impact in determining the job satisfaction and further recommends on adaptation of transformational leadership style to improve universities effectiveness'.

Atif Saleem et al (2020) investigated on the leadership styles practiced by Principal's at private secondary school on teachers' job performance with four leadership styles on individual job performance of teachers with structural equation model was analyzed to explore the effectiveness in determination of job performance. the results revealed that directive leadership has a significant impact in comparison with supportive, achievement and participative leadership form in non-western culture.

Arpit Shankdhar (2016) explained in the research article explains the present status of higher education system and its working conditions in India along with the importance and relevance of leadership styles practiced by Principal's in determining the job performance of employees. Leadership styles of Principals are linked with academic excellence and performance at university level in order to match the global standards.

Munir and Iqbal (2018) explored the relationship between Leadership Styles of Principals and Job Satisfaction of Teachers in Colleges for Women in the province of Punjab. With quantitative analysis in order to find out the relationship of leadership styles impact on teachers job satisfaction. Correlation analysis was used to find the relationship that exists between leadership and job satisfaction of teachers. The results revealed that transformational and transactional leadership style practice by principals had a positive relationship in determining the job satisfaction of teachers.

Harris et al (2016) investigated on the intention of employee staying at higher education institutions and the factor contributing to the job satisfaction of teachers with structural equation model using the dimensions of servant leadership style and the results reveals that the teachers job satisfaction for teachers and intention to stay at colleges is positively co related with leadership styles practiced by the principals practicing the servant leadership practices.

Georgolopoulos, Papaloi & Loukorou (2018) studied the degree of application of servant leadership style as well as degree of job satisfaction perceived by teachers to examine the correlation between servant leadership styles of Principals' with teachers job satisfaction. The study was undertaken with 141 teachers from 20 public primary school in the prefecture of Trikala in central Greece.

The study reveals that the servant leadership gives value to the people, allotment of authority, the implementation of authenticity, contributes to the improvement and development of people. Teachers are found to be happy under the servant leadership practice of Principal's. Correlation analysis statistically demonstrated a strong positive relationship on the perceived teachers job satisfaction which also contribute for the smooth functioning effectiveness' of school environment.

Sonika Singh (2020) examine the role of Servant leadership behaviour of school Principal's and its impact on job satisfaction. Data were collected from 728 secondary school teachers belonging to Himachal Pradesh a state of north India. Using a multi stage probability sampling techniques mean, correlation structural equation model were employed in the data analysis to test the hypothesis. The results revealed a significant effect of servant leadership on teachers job satisfaction and Principal's exhibited the servant leadership qualities to improve the job satisfaction level of teachers working with them.

Greeni Maheshwari (2021) conducted exploratory research in the public high school in the southern region of Vietnam to understand the influence of transformational and transactional leadership style on teachers job satisfaction and job performance. Quantitative study was initiated two stage cluster sampling method was adopted to collect the data from 18 public high schools which included 144 teachers working in the schools.

The results revealed a positive relationship was identified with transformational leadership whereas negative relationship with transactional leadership on teachers job satisfaction and job performance. In the study the research also revealed that job satisfaction as a mediating variable between the principal's leadership and teachers job performance.

Ali & Dahie (2015) investigated the impact of transactional, transformational laissez fair leadership form on teachers job satisfaction. The study was undertaken with descriptive design to analyse from 200 respondents from secondary school teachers in Somalia state. The researcher used regression analysis and checked the outliers and collinearity for checking the violation. The researcher found that the three dimension of leadership style practices of Principal's had significant and positive impact on teachers job satisfaction in Somalia state.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Statement of the problem:

The relationship between Principal's leadership styles and Job Satisfaction of a teachers working at Degree Colleges in North Bangalore City.

3.2. Objectives of the Study:

1. To understand the educational leadership and Job satisfaction prospects at higher educational institutions in India.
2. To asses the different leadership Styles practiced by College Principals at degree colleges in North Bangalore City
3. To research the effect of leadership method in determining the job satisfaction of Degree college teachers.

Hypothesis 1: There is no evidence of difference in different types of leadership style adopted by college Principals at Degree Colleges in North Bangalore City

Hypothesis 2: There is no relationship between the leadership styles of college Principals in determining teachers Job satisfaction working with them.

3.3. Population of the study:

The research had a focus group of teachers working at degree colleges in North Bangalore City, whose role was varied and had different dimension as in comparison with the teachers at school level. Principal leadership style and its perseverance was of different level at colleges as it is believed that Principals and teachers together deliver a value-added service to the students over all development. This unique demand of understanding principal leadership style and teachers job satisfaction has guided in continuing with sample selection.

The units considered for this research is the lecturers or teachers working at private degree colleges within the boundaries of North Bangalore city.

3.4. Sample of the study

There are nearly 300 private colleges in the city limits; for the research purpose I have chosen 10 degree colleges from the entire population as the sample, further a sample of 120 respondents was drawn from the major streams of degree college level.

3.5. Details of sample collection

Number of self-finance colleges	10
Total number of respondents	120
Male respondents	53
Female respondents	67

The questionnaire contains 25 questions that are broadly clubbed into 4 dimensions as given below

List of Parameters

Number	Parameters
1	Servant Leadership Technique
2	Transformational Leadership technique
3	Transactional Leadership technique
4	Laissez Fair leadership technique
5	Job satisfaction

Reliability Result: Cronbach's alpha

Reliability of leadership style and job satisfaction questionnaire

Cronbach's alpha test for leadership style	No of items
0.819	25
Cronbach's alpha test for job satisfaction	No of items
0.825	10

As Cronbach's alpha (0.819) and (0.825) is bigger than 0.70, with this we can statistically decide that there is an inter-reliability and density in assessing different items of leadership style and job satisfaction questionnaire.

3.6. Limitations of the study:

1. The study limits to the teachers working at Degree colleges in North Bangalore City.
2. Leadership Styles and its relationship in determining the job satisfaction of teachers and the other variables are considered to be neutral.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

It deals with the analysis of the data collected, interpretation and discussion on the results. The Statistical software i.e. SPSS 23 version were utilized for the examination of the collected data.

Concepts of Educational Leadership:

The most prominent form of leadership which is identified and practiced by educational leaders are as under:

Servant leadership style: This form of leaders put the followers first, leaders have high level of trust confidence on followers. It is identified as end goal approach and empower the subordinates to promote innovative ideas, empower them by involving in decision making process. Servant leaders aim at developing leadership quality in others, they demonstrate the characteristics of empathy, stewardship, listening, commitment to the personal growth of others.

Transformational Leadership Style: This form of leadership is most predominant form of leadership where the leaders inspire the followers through their action, they are more energetic, enthusiastic and passionate about their work. This form of leaders focus on helping every member of the group and assist them in achieving the goals of the organisation. Transformational leadership style was coined by Brun's in 1978 and includes the features such as creating an inspiring vision of the future, motivating people in achieving their goals and building stronger trust-based relationship with the subordinates.

Transactional Leadership style: This form of leadership is also referred as managerial leadership where leaders focus on instructing followers to abide by the rules and recognize and reward and punish the followers. It is based on exchange of transactions the roles are established with protocols and procedures. The main focus is on achieving organizational goals which is strictly monitored by the leaders and complete decision making will be in the hands of leaders.

Laissez Fair Leadership Style: This form of leadership is also referred as passive leadership, where in the leaders have complete trust and reliance on the subordinators, avoid or give very little instructions or guidance to subordinates. The

subordinators have complete freedom in decision making as leaders will not involve themselves in the decision making process, the followers use their creativity and resources and experiences to help to meet their goals.

Prospects of Job Satisfaction

It is very much essential for the institutions to have the quality pupil to serve the institution and also to help students to achieve their goals. Every educational institution will make sure to have the good quality staff who work together at institutional success. Therefore, keeping the staff more satisfied at their work will become an essential point of success. A satisfied teacher is one who has passion about the work and satisfied professionally and financially. Finding the right place and position to work needs tremendous contribution from the leaders who support them at the personal and institutional goals. Therefore, understanding job satisfaction aspect of teachers is very essential which has a greater influence and foundation of job satisfaction theories which are:

Herzberg Two factor Theory: The theory was developed in 1959, Herzberg identified major two factors which affects employees at work place. Job satisfaction was broadly associated with 'Motivators' and 'Hygiene' factor. Motivational factors generates job satisfaction and hygiene factor must be present to contribute for job satisfaction. The theory emphasizes on job enrichment and the leader must focus on motivational factors which can improve work quality and also hygiene factors must be taken care for not keeping the employees dissatisfied.

Locke's Value Theory: The theory was conceptualized by E A Locke. The theory is based on job satisfaction which occurs where job outcome an employee receives must match with those desired by them. The more outcome the employees receives with value they more they are satisfied.

Adam's Equity Theory: Contributed by J S Adam explained that employee job satisfaction and motivation is measured in terms of input and output factors. Input factors consists of age, education, social status, Organisational position qualification, hard work etc. and output signified rewards, pay, status and promotion. The relationship between an individual inputs and their benefits(output) is essential for fair and equitable working environment.

Job Characteristic Model: Hackman and Oldham (1976) specified the conditions under which the people are satisfied by their work and motivated to perform effectively. According this theory the core dimensions of job satisfaction includes skill identity, task identity, task significance, autonomy and feedback. The theory emphasized that task in itself motivate the employees therefore restructuring those task will make employees stay motivated at their job.

With the above job satisfaction and motivation theories Herzberg two factor theory is being adopted to identify the college Teachers job satisfaction at degree colleges in Bangalore cit

Purposive sampling method was adapted to select the number of colleges from higher educational institutions. Descriptive correlation analysis is utilized to carry out in the current study. Outcomes on consecutive proportions are illustrated on Mean, SD (Min-Max) and findings on categorical distributions are illustrated in Number (PERCENTAGE). Importance is evaluated at 5% level of implication.

Table 4.1: Demographic details of Respondents

Profile Details	Total Number	Percentage
Gender		
Male	53	44
female	67	56
Age in years		
23- 30 years	15	12
31-35 years	38	32
36-40 years	55	46
>40 years	12	10
Work experience in years		
< 5	7	6
6-10	41	34
11-15	48	40
>15	24	20
Subject Stream		
Commerce	65	54
Arts	31	26
Science	24	20

Table 4.2: Prospects of Leadership style Practices and Job Satisfaction of teachers at Degree Colleges in North Bangalore

Leadership Style Practices	Number of items	Max score	Mean score	Median score	SD
Servant Leadership Technique	10	40	38	39	1.92
Transformational technique	5	20	16.5	17	1.89
Transactional technique	5	20	15.5	16	2.33
Laissez fair technique	5	20	4.85	4	3.80
Teachers Job Satisfaction					
Motivational Factors	5*	25	19.25	19	2.65
Hygiene Factors	5	25	19.35	19.5	4.87

Table 4.3: Results of correlation Coefficient at Degree colleges in North Bangalore

Leadership Style	Correlation Coefficient	Significance level (P value)
Servant Leadership Style	0.783	0.001**
Transformational leadership Style	0.523	0.001**
Transactional leadership Style	0.114	0.483
Laissez fair Leadership Style	-0.423	0.006**

(**correlation is significant at 0.001 level)

From the above table it is very much evident that leadership style of Principals at colleges has a relationship on the teacher's job satisfaction. Servant Leadership style and Transformational leadership style exhibits a moderate correlation leadership technique and job satisfaction of teachers and P value is lesser than the standard prescribed (0.05) hence we can statistically prove that Servant Leadership transformational leadership technique has an influence on the job/ work satisfaction of teachers at colleges. Whereas transactional leadership style demonstrates a weak correlation and P value is greater than 0.05 which confirms that there is no proper evidence to show that transactional leadership style has an impact on job satisfaction of teachers and statistically fails to prove the relationship. Laissez fair leadership has negative correlation which means leadership style and job satisfaction of teachers tend

to move on the opposite side which is statistically proved with P value being lesser than 0.05.

Testing of Hypothesis:

Hypothesis 1: There is no evidence of difference in different types of leadership style adopted by college Principals at Degree Colleges in North Bangalore City

From the above analysis it is very much evident that there is an evidence of difference in different types of leadership styles adopted by college principals at Degree colleges with different mean scores. Therefore, hypothesis 1 is contradicted and alternative hypothesis is adopted.

Hypothesis 2: There is no relationship between the leadership styles of college Principals in determining teachers Job satisfaction working with them.

From the above results of correlation coefficient it is evident that there certainly is a significant connection between leadership techniques of college principals on teacher's job satisfaction by working with them. Significance level is determined by P value which is >0.005 . thus, Hypothesis 2 is rescinded and alternative hypothesis is adopted.

5. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. Respondents from degree colleges were drawn by assuring and giving proper weightage for gender selection, in order to get the unbiased information from the respondents.
2. Majority of teachers at degree colleges belong to the age group of 36-40 which shows the teachers are more experienced with 6 to 10 years in the profession.
3. Teachers at degree colleges were majorly found in commerce stream in comparison with art and science.
4. The leadership style under study includes four major types of leadership style which was chosen after proper scrutiny of existing leadership style which is very well practiced in the educational field.
5. At degree colleges in Bangalore north city, it was found that both Servant leadership and transformational leadership has been practiced by the principal which accounted for maximum mean score whereas Laissez fair leadership style having the least mean score.
6. Job satisfactions of teachers are being measured in two broad dimensions which were categorized as motivational and hygiene factors which determine the level of satisfaction. At degree colleges the respondents exhibited high level of satisfaction with the mean score of 19.25
7. Pearson's correlation was utilized to analyze the correlation between the Principal leadership style and teachers job satisfaction at the degree colleges and it was found that in servant leadership and transformational leadership style had a moderate correlation was evidenced but with a significant P value (0.001)
8. Correlation coefficient was negative in terms of laissez fair leadership style at self private colleges at -0.423 which shows that there is no impact of leadership style in determining the job satisfaction of teachers at university affiliated colleges in north Bangalore city.

6. CONCLUSION

At the completion of the analysis it is evident from the study that Leadership practices practiced by Principals at Degree Colleges has an evident relationship in determining the job satisfaction of teachers working with them. The Descriptive Statistical Analysis has helped us to conclude various observations on the Perception of Leadership Styles.

In multi-cultural organisation especially in India, different categories of people with different culture work for the development of students. Therefore, it is very much evident that perception of people will not be the same in all the aspects in the working environment. In this prospect the role of leaders becomes utmost important in keeping the people together and motivate them to work better. It is the responsibility of the Leader to diffuse such situations, diagnose the problem and identify collectively multiple solutions for a single problem. Such Leaders have been highly successful and effective in implementing their Leadership role and which would surely contribute in determining the job satisfaction of teachers and their overall development

Executing a research project on a theme like Leadership is certainly a learning experience, especially being a principal of a degree institute or university. Time and again researches and analysis endeavors on Leadership, particularly on Educational Leadership (Principals) has been executed all over the globe and proportions have been jotted down. However, this research work has distinctly made me understand and apply those concepts of Leadership in a specific context of degree colleges in North Bangalore city colleges.

References

- 1) Arpit Shankhdhar and Rashmi Mehrotra (2016) Excellence in Higher Education: Link With College Principals' Leadership Styles, Indian journal of applied research Volume :6 | Issue : 5 | May 2016 | ISSN - 2249-555X | IF : 3.919 | IC Value : 74.50IT
- 2) Kenya Harris, Lynette Hinds, Sherry Manansingh,, Michael Rubino, and Elsa Sofia Morote, Ed.D.(2016), What type of Leadership in Higher Education Promotes Job Satisfaction and Increases Retention? Spring 2016, Journal of Leadership and Instruction pp 27-31
- 3) Hina Munir and Muhammad Zafar Iqbal (2018) 'A Study of Relationship between Leadership Styles of Principals and Job Satisfaction of Teachers in Colleges for Women' *Bulletin of Education and Research August 2018, Vol. 40, No. 2 pp. 65-78*
- 4) Shadi Hijazi, Abdul Latif Kasim Yaakob Daud (2016), 'Leadership Styles and Their Relationship with the Private University Employees' Job Satisfaction in United Arab Emirates' *Journal of Public Administration and Governance* ISSN 2161-7104 2016, Vol. 6, No. 4. Pp:110-124
- 5) Atif Saleem Sarfraz Aslam Hong-biao Yin and Congman Rao (2020) 'Principal Leadership Styles and Teacher Job Performance: Viewpoint of Middle Management', *Sustainability* **2020**, 12, 3390; doi:10.3390/su12083390
- 6) Northouse, P. G. 2004. Leadership: theory and practice, 6th ed., California, CA: Sage Publications, Inc.
- 7) Dutta, V. and Sahney, S. (2016), "School leadership and its impact on student achievement: The mediating role of school climate and teacher job satisfaction", *International Journal of Educational Management*, Vol. 30 No. 6, pp. 941-958. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-12-2014-0170>
- 8) Cogaltay, N., Yalcin, M., & Karadag, E. (2016). Educational leadership and job satisfaction of teachers: A meta-analysis study on the studies published between 2000 and 2016 in Turkey. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 16(62).

- 9) Maheshwari, G. (2021). Influence of teacher-perceived transformational and transactional school leadership on teachers' job satisfaction and performance: A case of Vietnam. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 1-15.
- 10) Ali, A. Y. S., & Dahie, A. M. (2015). Leadership style and teacher job satisfaction: Empirical survey from secondary schools in Somalia. *Leadership*, 5(8), 33-29.
- 11) Sharma, R. D., & Jyoti, J. (2009). Job satisfaction of university teachers: an empirical study. *Journal of Services Research*, 9(2).
- 12) Singh, Sonika & Ryhal, Piar. (2020). How Does Servant Leadership Behaviour Affect Job Satisfaction? A Study on Indian Academia. *FIIB Business Review*. 10. 231971452096869. 10.1177/2319714520968697.
- 13) Armstrong, M. (2006). *A Handbook of Human resource Management Practice*, Tenth Edition, Kogan Page Publishing, London, , p. 264
- 14) Vroom, V.H. (1964). *Work and motivation*, John Wiley and Sons, New York, p.99
- 15) Source: Steptoe-Warren (*Occupational Psychology*, 2013, p. 174)
- 16) <https://positivepsychology.com/job-satisfaction-theory/>